

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Modelling of mechanical behaviour of MXene/polymer nanocomposites

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MXenes – novel 2D nanoparticles

Babak Anasori, Michael Naguib, Yury Gogotsi, Michel W. Barsoum. Drexel University, 2011

FEM

S, Mises
(GPa)

VS

MD

Periodic unit cell (PUC)

Material	Young's modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Deformation at break (%)	Poisson's ratio
Ti ₃ C ₂ [1]	502	22000	6.5	0.23
PVA [2]	0.92	32	13.8	0.4

2D – 3D RVE models

Stress distribution – PUC and 2D RVE

(b) S, Mises (MPa)

straight flakes

(c)

waved flakes

(d)

edged flakes

Stress distribution – 3D RVE

Results: PUC, 2D – 3D RVE

RVE anisotropy and shape analysis

PVA and Epoxy comparison

10 v% Ti_3C_2 : random distribution vs aligned

1. Y.-K. Yang, L.-J. Yu, R.-G. Peng, Y.-L. Huang, Ch.-E. He, H.-Y. Liu, X.-B. Wang, X.-L. Xie and Y.-W. Mai "Incorporation of liquid-like multiwalled carbon nanotubes into an epoxy matrix by solvent-free processing". *Nanotechnology*, Vol. 23. pp 1-10, 2012.
2. Z. Ling *et al.*, "Flexible and conductive MXene films and nanocomposites with high capacitance," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 111, no. 47, pp. 16676–16681, 2014.

Conclusions

- The strength of the interphase layer was obtained the same as the strength of PVA.
- Homogenised Young's modulus of multi-layered MXenes inside PVA matrix is estimated for 13 GPa.
- RVE with randomly distributed flakes can be considered as a homogeneous composite.
- MXenes can be defined in a circular shape.
- RVE with aligned flakes resulted in higher Young's modulus and strength when compared with randomly distributed flakes.

Thank You for attention

Nano2Day

Multifunctional polymer composites doped with novel 2D nanoparticles for advanced applications

Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 777810.

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